

**CLASSIFICATION OF THE DEGREE OF BLEEDING ACTIVITY ACCORDING TO
ENDOSCOPIC SIGNS**

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***Annotation.** The research methods related to the epidemiological part of the work included the calculation of absolute data on the registration and recording of cases of the disease and its complications, the calculation of the dynamics of the intensive indicator, as well as a number of areas of study of the structure of patients by sex and age. For an objective distribution of patients by age groups, the classification of age groups adopted at a special symposium in Kyiv in 1962 and a seminar of the regional office of the World Health Organization (Kyiv, 1963) was used. According to this classification, persons under 19 years of age were classified as a juvenile group, 20-44 years old as a young group, 45-59 years old as a middle (mature) group, 60-74 years old as an elderly group, 75-90 years old as an old age group, and over 90 years old as a long-livers group (V.V. Frolkis, 1970). The number of patients in each analyzed age group is presented both in absolute and relative figures (%) to the total number of patients.*

***Key words:** biochemical epidemiology, gastrit, duadenid, anémia, gastroenterology.*

Introduction. In the clinical part of the presented studies, the same form of distribution of patients in age groups is preserved. In this part, a comprehensive examination was performed, including traditional clinical, biochemical, instrumental studies for a polypositional constructive assessment of the condition of a patient with cirrhosis with active ongoing or already stopped bleeding from the varices and veins.

This assessment is based on taking into account the signs of cirrhosis activity, decompensation of portal circulation and the degree of encephalopathy, the severity and extent of the varices and veins, the level of the bleeding source, the degree of blood loss. It provides for the selection of groups of patients with varying degrees of probability of developing fatal complications in the postoperative period from the number of admitted patients with cirrhosis

with bleeding from the varices and veins, and therefore determining the feasibility of a particular method of treatment, including surgical intervention. It is impossible to establish the severity and prognosis of liver cirrhosis by a single functional test. Therefore, various test systems have been proposed for this purpose. The first proposal of this kind - the Child-Turcotte criteria scheme (1964) was made by specialists in the field of surgical hepatology for patients with cirrhosis

Materials and methods of research. The technique of using the Child-Turcotte and Child-Pugh criteria is the same: one indicator of group A was estimated at 1 point, the same indicator in group B was estimated at 2 points, and in group C - at 3 points. Based on such approaches, three groups are distinguished according to the total criteria: the first group - 5-7 points, the second group - 8-10 points, and the third group - 11 points or more. This system is quite reliable in determining the severity of the disease, its prognosis, and is especially valuable when deciding on surgical treatment of a patient

Of the special laboratory data for working with these schemes, it is sufficient to use, and was used in the work:

1. Determination of the level of total blood protein using the Kingsley refractometric method (g / l) - with a normal indicator of 65-85
2. Determination of total blood bilirubin using the Jendrassik, Qleghorn method (mmol / l) - with a normal indicator of 4.6-13.5;
3. Coagulating ability of blood according to the prothrombin index according to Quick (%) - with the norm of 70-100;

Specific signs of any bleeding are also characteristic of bleeding from the varicose veins - a drop in blood pressure, severity of tachycardia, deficiency of circulating blood volume, a decrease in the number of red blood cells, hemoglobin level, and hematocrit according to laboratory indicators.

These signs are the basis for assessing the severity of bleeding according to the classification of V.I. Struchkov (1978);

Grade I - the general condition is relatively satisfactory. Minor changes in hemodynamics; the pulse is slightly increased, blood pressure is within normal limits. Hemoglobin is above 100 g / l. The deficit in circulating blood volume did not exceed 5% of normal.

Grade II - general condition of moderate severity. Lethargy, dizziness, fainting, pale skin are noted. From the hemodynamic parameters - significant increase in heart rate, decrease in blood pressure to 90 mm Hg. Deficit of total circulating blood flow is 15% of the expected value, hemoglobin is 80 g / l. Grade III - general condition is severe. Skin is pale, covered with cold sweat, severe thirst. Pulse is frequent, threadlike. Blood pressure is reduced to 60 mm Hg. Deficit of total circulating blood flow is 30% of the expected value, hemoglobin is 60 g / l. Grade I - profuse bleeding with loss of consciousness. General condition is extremely severe, bordering on sagonal. Deficit of total circulating blood flow is more than 30% of the expected value, hemoglobin is below 60 g / l. Disappearance of pulse and blood pressure is possible. It is important to remember that the decrease in hemoglobin content due to hemodilution begins to be detected only several hours after the onset of bleeding. The shock index according to the Algover method (defined as the quotient of the pulse rate divided by the systolic pressure) helps in assessing the deficit in circulating blood volume.

Results and discussion. Depending on the volume of blood loss and the magnitude of the circulating blood volume deficit according to Algover, three degrees of severity of acute gastrointestinal bleeding are distinguished. It is known that bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract is characterized by massive blood loss, where the BCC deficit, as a rule, exceeds the 5% threshold. This determined the advisability of combining the 1st and 2nd degrees of blood loss according to the classification of V.I. Struchkov into a single one for patients with cirrhosis with bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract and made it possible to unify it with the definition of the shock index according to Algover, thus identifying only three degrees of blood loss. Instrumental research methods. Examination of the esophagus and stomach was performed in all patients with cirrhosis upon admission to the hospital with suspected bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract by esophagogastroscope with a fiber optic endoscopic apparatus from Olympus (Japan). The severity of varicose veins of the esophagus and stomach was assessed according to the classification developed by Scherzinger A.G. (1986), according to which three degrees are distinguished: I - the diameter of varicose veins is 2-3 mm. II - the diameter of varicose veins is 3-5 mm. III - the diameter of varicose veins is more than 5 mm. According to the localization of varicose veins, the stomach is distinguished, where the veins are located mainly in the cardiofundal section, and the esophagus, where the dilated veins can spread only to its lower third, lower and middle third, or be visualized totally along its entire length. Endoscopic examination allows to verify the source of bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract in 70% of cases, and the proposed classification of the degree of bleeding activity by

endoscopic signs J. Forrest (1974) systematized them (Table 2.4). Thus, depending on the endoscopic picture in patients with peptic ulcer, active and established gastrointestinal bleeding are distinguished. In turn, active bleeding can be endoscopically manifested as spurting bleeding (the so-called Forrest Ia type), bleeding with slow release of blood (Forrest Ib type), bleeding with slow release of blood from under an adjacent thrombus. Established bleeding is endoscopically characterized by the detection of a thrombus or superficially located blood clots in the area of the ulcer bottom with a visible section of a non-bleeding blood vessel.

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